

STUDENTS AWARENESS TOWARDS SMART BOARD TECHNOLOGY (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO POLLACHI TALUK)

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Abstract:

This paper investigate the effect of smart class room learning on the performance of first grade student in English subject the present study is an conducted in Coimbatore district pollachi. The objective of the study is to know the smart class technological methods and details of the new concepts for develop the learning ability of students and to provide use of SWOT analysis of smart class as technology and to study the interactional effort of smart classroom teaching conventional teaching genders the achievement. to improve quality of education by providing quality content. The data for the study have been collected by the way structured questionnaire in order to know the student's preference and satisfaction on smart board classroom of the total questionnaire issued, 120 questionnaires are collected and 120 questionnaires are taken for analysis. Convenient sampling method is adopted to select the sampling students. The simple percentage and weighted average and chi- square test are the tools applied in analyzing data. It is found from the present study that there has been a positive approach about the smart board technology

Key Words: Awareness, Smart Board & Approach

Introduction:

Learning is not how much one cramp up. It's rather the knowledge that remains after one forgets what he/she learned in schools. Thus we emphasize in learning that concepts with the help of visuals and activities. To keep such view the smart class learning was introduced. In today competitive world the child needs the skill sets, which are beyond subject knowledge and require concentration, assimilation power and retention. In this regard the role of smart class is quite important. Smart class is introduced by educomp. Educomp is one of the largest education companies in India taking care of entire education life cycle of students. The company currently works with over 26000 schools and over 15millions learners and educators across the world. Smart class is digitalized class room, which is rapidly transforming the way teachers teach and students learn in schools with innovative and meaningful use of technology, powered by the world's largest repository of digital content mapped to Indian school curriculum, smart class bring in technology right blackboard for teachers in the classroom. The teaching material performs as better learning material, was found to be effective compare to the traditional method of teaching. Smart classroom technology is known as interactive white board that is used by classroom all over. The interactive white board is huge screen that is mounted to a wall of the classroom.

Review of Literature:

Dr. Anita Menon (2015) her study on "effectiveness of smart class board teaching on the achievement in chemistry of secondary school students" analysed that the academic achievement in chemistry of secondary school students when taught through smart class room teaching show greater achievement then connectional teaching as well as there is no gender difference in the academic achievement in the chemistry of secondary school students when taught through smart class room teaching and conventional teaching and interaction of gender and teaching method do not significantly affect the academic achievement in chemistry of secondary school students.

Dr. Johnson (2002) his study on "Effective and attitude for smart class" has conclude that identify the various pros and cons of emerging new technology of smart class in the field of education and also helps to increasing their conceptual clarity especially in the subject that require practical application and visual understanding easy to learn and memorizing. But this technology also has certain disadvantage. It is observed that use of smart class had lead to deterioration in the writing skills of students and there thinking abilities. The future of smart class is skill to mature.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the smart class technological methods and details of the new concepts for develop the learning ability of students
- ✓ To provide use of SWOT analysis of smart class as technology

- ✓ To study the interactional effort of smart classroom teaching conventional teaching genders the achievement.
- ✓ To improve quality of education by providing quality content.

Research Methodology:

The present study is mainly based on primary data which is collected from the respondents of pollachi taluk through by distributing the questionnaire. The questionnaire contains question relating to the personal profile of sample respondents awareness and satisfaction of the smart class.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

In this chapter, the data collected have analyzed and interpreted using statistical techniques namely simple percentage. The questions were raised in order to enquire about their student aware on SBT classes. The socio- economic profile of the respondents has been evaluated by using simple percentage analysis and the results are summarized in the following table shown below.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Area of Resident		
Urban	27	22.50%
Semi Urban	64	53.33%
Rural	29	24.16%
Age		
Upto 15 Years	2	1%
16 To 25 Years	106	71%
26 To 35 Years	28	19%
Above 36 Years	14	9%
Gender		
Male	37	30.84%
Female	83	69.16%
Marital Status		
Married	50	33%
Un Married	100	67%
Educational Qualification		
SSLC	37	30.83
H.Sc	43	35.83
UG Degree	12	10
PG Degree	28	23.34
Number of Student Are Studying Family		
1	27	22.52
2	59	49.16
3	29	24.16
4 And Above	5	4.16
Board of Study		
State Board	60	50
CBSE	60	50
Type of Family		
Low Level Student	23	19.17
Medium Level Student	59	49.16
High Level Student	38	31.67
Amount Spend Per Year		
Rs.1000-3000	17	14.16
Rs.3001-5000	65	54.16
Rs.5001-7500	31	30
Rs.7500 Above	5	1.6
Session Of Hour		
Morning Session	60	50
Afternoon Session	45	37.5
Evening Session	15	12.5

Hour Are Spent Per Day		
One Hour	19	15.83
Two Hour	65	54.17
Three Hour	31	25.83
More Than 4 Hour	5	4.17
Method are Mostly Used		
Traditional Method	33	27.5
Discussion Method	47	39.16
Demonstration Method	7	5.84
Power Point Method	33	27.5
Types of Smart Class System are Available		
Educomp	15	12.5
The Smart	77	64.16
The RTIVC	4	3.33
DIGI Class	24	20
Types of Technologies Uses		
Slide Presentation	49	40.83
Audio & Video	50	41.66
Shared With Board	21	17.5
Best Way of SBT Teaching		
Black Board Teaching	32	26.66
Smart Class Teaching	88	73.33
Processing System are Use to Increase Mark and Understand		
Videos	27	22.5
Forum Discussion	66	55
Practice Test	27	22.5
Information to Best Way of Learning and to Know About SBT		
Friends	37	30.83
Relatives	49	40.83
Colleague	32	26.66
Online Advertisement	0	0
Offline Advertisement	2	1.6
Other (Specify)	0	0
Process and Creativity of Awareness		
News Paper Advertisement	52	43.33
Magazine	45	37.5
Television	19	15.83
Radio	4	3.33
Use SBT to Use of Note Book Cost Per Year		
Yes	89	74.16
No	31	25.83
Yes		
Rs.300-500	26	21.66
Rs.501-700	54	45
Rs.701-900	8	6.6
Rs.900 Above	1	0.83
Blank	31	25.83
Mostly Areas of Use		
Conference	22	18.33
Exhibition	57	47.5
Meeting	29	24.16
Class Room	12	10

Hence the majority of the respondents belong to 13 and 15 years age group. Hence the majority of the respondents 64(53.33%) resides in rural area. Hence the majority of the respondents 43(35.83%) are HSC. Hence the majority of the respondents 59(49.16%) are the 2 members. It observed out of 120 respondents, 60(50%) are state board, 60(50%) are CBSE. Hence both the state board and CBSC are same level of

respondent. Hence the majority of the respondents 59(49.16%) are medium level student. Hence the majority of respondents 65(54.16%) belong to the person. Hence the majority of the respondents are 65(54.17%) hour spent per day. the respondents like that afternoon session, and 15(12.5%) are like that evening session. Hence the majority of the respondents 60(50%) feel like that morning session. Hence the majority of the respondents are using 47(39.16%) of discussion method Hence the majority of the respondents are using 77(64.16%) of the smart class are use. Hence the majority of the respondents are use 50(41.66%) to Audio & Video technology Hence the majority of the respondents are using 55 (45.88%) power point presentations. Hence the majority of the students are like that 88(73.33%) Smart Class Teaching Hence the majority of the respondents are using 66(55.00%) of forum discussion. Hence the majority of the respondents are using 49 (40.83%) are known about the relatives. Out of 120 respondents, 89(74.16%) of the respondents are accepted that they are using highly spent per year but 31(25.83%) of the respondents are accepted as No. Hence the majority of the respondents are accepted as highly spent per year. Hence the majority of the user is 57(47.50%) Exhibition.

Table 2: Factors Affecting the Level of Satisfaction on Smart Board

Variables	X2 Value	DF	Table Value 5% Level
Area of residence	14.302	4	9.488
Age	8.181	6	12.592
Gender	4.000	2	5.991
Educational and level of awareness	17.937	6	12.592
Number of studying in your family	13.473	6	12.592
Board of studying	7.386	2	5.991

Significant at five percent level

The percentage of respondents who have high level of awareness is high among respondents belongs to age 13-15 years while low of level of awareness in high among respondents belong to 16-18 years. Hence, it is observed that respondents belong to below13-15 years are with high level of awareness. As calculated Chi-square value is less than the table at 1 percent level and 5 percent level, there does not exist any significant associated between age and level of awareness. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The percentage of respondents who have high level of awareness is high among female respondents while low level of awareness is high among male respondents. Hence, it is observed that female respondents are with high level of awareness. As calculated Chi-square value is less than the table at 1 percent level and 5 percent level, there does exist significant associated between gender and level of awareness. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The percentage of respondents who have high level of awareness is high among respondents belongs to age Urban while low of level of awareness in high among respondents belong to Semi-Urban. Hence, it is observed that respondents belong to urban are with high level of awareness. As calculated Chi-square value is less than the table at 1 percent level and 5 percent level, there does not exist any significant associated between areas of school study. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Weighted Average Rank to SBT:

The following table was prepared Awareness on Smart Board Technology in classroom through weighted average rank.

Awareness on Smart Board Technology through Weighted Average Rank to SBT:

Factors	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	Total	Rank
High cost spent to SBT Study	17	20	17	33	12	10	11	120	I
Highly words has use to SBT Study	21	8	22	16	18	8	27	120	III
More use age of SBT to private school/college than govt school	19	16	19	23	19	18	6	120	II
SBT System have more use full to private school /college in URBAN areas	30	10	16	14	22	15	13	120	II
This study are more use full for higher level family students	7	24	20	6	20	18	25	120	V
Mostly this system have use and benefit to highly educate of parent's students	16	17	17	19	5	29	17	120	IV
In this system has use to reduce and easy understand	10	25	9	9	24	22	21	120	V

It is observed from the above table that among the Aware of “High cost spent to SBT Study” gets the first rank. Followed by “Highly Words Has Use to SBT Study” and also “SBT System has more use full to private school /college in URBAN areas” both are get second rank. Third rank gets for “Highly words has use to SBT Study”. Forth rank gets for “Mostly This System Have Use and Benefit to Highly Educate of Parent’s Students”. Fifth rank gets for “This study are more use full for higher level family students” and also “In This System Has Use to Reduce and Easy Understand”.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents 42(35%) belongs to the age group of 13-15 years.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 83(69%) are female.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 64(53%) resides in Urban area
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 43(36%) educational qualification.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 59(49%) students are studying in your family members.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 60(50%) both state board and CBSC are same study of board.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 59(49%) medium level of family members are mostly use.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 65(54%) amount are spent to per year for SBT.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 60(50%) morning session are mostly spent for SBT class.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 65(54%) one hour are spent per day to SBT class.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 47(40%) Traditional methods are mostly used into SBT class.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 77(64%) the smart type of class are available in schools and college.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 50(42%) Audio & video technologies are mostly use in SBT class.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 55(46%) Power point presentation processing system have use to easy understand and take notes
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 88(73%) smart class teaching to best way for SBT teaching.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 66(55%) Forum discussion processing systems are mostly use to increase mark and easy understand.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 49(41%) relatives inform to best way of learning and to know about SBT class.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 52(43%) News paper advertisement to know creativity of awareness for SBT class.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 54(45%) are 501-700 amount spent per year.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 57(47%) Exhibition types of area are mostly use.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 86(72%) use of SBT for study and revise are highly satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 75(63%) SBT has helps to better attention and lesson are satisfied
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 84(70%) SBT can improved for smart class syllabus oriented and knowledge are satisfied
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 66(55%) make learn and enjoyable are highly satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 43(36%) academic performance to teach are satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 48(40%) mostly use to experimental teaching to student are highly satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 52(43%) highly reduce of cost to take class are satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 49(41%) E-class cost compared with annual fees is dissatisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 44(37%) relationship between students and teachers for use of SBT tools are satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents 70(58%) fix the fees to SBT are satisfied.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Practical class should be provided
- ✓ It will be more reliable if they provide online lecture class.
- ✓ Interactive session should be introduced
- ✓ Video classes should be included instead of power point presentation.
- ✓ Lessons should be presented in story way.
- ✓ Smart class learning should also be connected with real world.

Conclusion:

The students who are high achievers have also scored better academic achievement taught through smart class and through traditional method. The reasons of performing well by high achievers may be motivation and reinforcement given to all students on every improvement because smart class created much interested than traditional method. Creation of enjoyable environment in class learning helped to develop cognitive dimension.

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